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CRITERIA EFFECTS THE DECISIONS IN THE SELECTION OF FACADES FOR THE TALL BUILDINGS IN UAE

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ABSTRACT

This is a research study as a part of detailed research on “a critical study of decision making process in the project management of facades for the tall buildings in UAE”. This study explore into the criteria effects the decisions in the selection of façades for the tall buildings in UAE. Façades of Tall buildings demands specific requirements to withstand the natural forces and to function the performance requirements as a wall without sacrificing the aesthetic requirements. Design, Engineering, Procurement, Fabrication, Installation and Maintenance of facades for the tall buildings faces various criterions such as Façade System Performance requirements, Aesthetics, Cost, Sustainability, Civil Defense and other statutory requirement Compliance. Initial research study shows that the façade selection decisions are influenced by the System performance requirements, Cost factor, Time factor and Aesthetics. Appropriate decisions in the selection of facades will avoid the construction risks such as failure of the facade system performance, function, accidents, increased operational costs etc. The parties involved in the decision making of facades project management are mainly the representatives of clients, architects & engineers, main contractors, facade specialist contractors, façade specialist consultants, statutory authorities, suppliers and manufactures etc. Decisions are sometimes being detrimentally influenced by personal intervention or will be forced to accept a compromise in the final stage due to cost and time impact with motivations of profit. Further study is proposed to explore the possibility of an integrated decision making system in the selection of façades and related materials for the tall buildings.

Key Words: - Tall buildings, Facades, Criteria, Performance, Decisions

1.1 Introduction

Regarding Tall buildings, façade or the envelope remains one of the most important exterior elements for building functionality. BS 6100 – 1:2004 defines Façade as the exterior

surface of a wall enclosing a building, which is usually non load bearing and which can include a curtain wall, cladding or some other exterior finish.

Envelope of the tall buildings helps to define the distinctive architectural aesthetics of the building and it also has the serious role related to functional performance as a wall. As know-how continues to progress, different possibilities for improvement become available for incorporation into building envelopes. These components improve the performance of the building envelope. By explanation, the metal curtain wall or cladding is an independent unit assembly with self-sufficient components that does not support the building structure. Even though many proprietary curtain wall or cladding systems are available in the facade industry, all systems do not have the same functional performance. An understanding on different types of facades, façade elements/components, performance requirements, design parameters, fabrication, installations and its maintenance requirement are significant to make decisions in the project management of facades.

A site survey has been conducted on 28 Super Tall buildings (Above 300m) in Dubai (CTBUH 2016), to identify the type of façades used for the external envelope. This study provided a clear understanding about the façades of Super Tall buildings in UAE. The main finding gained through this study is that majority of the façades of Super Tall buildings are Aluminum and glazed curtain wall especially Unitized Curtain wall type of Construction. Such façades has mandatory performance requirements such as sustainability / green building, thermal insulation performance requirements from Municipality and Civil defense requirement on fire Stop.

For commercial or residential buildings, the envelope components, especially, the curtain wall provides few key functions: Weather barrier against the environmental factors for air penetration and water infiltration and light transmittance to the interior space. Considering the function of these components, we have to address building performance and access or improve the dynamics related to the environment. Sometimes architects or engineers employs wrong material choices and system application to environment due to a lack of understanding or familiarity of said systems. This high lights the importance of proper selection facades for the buildings.

1.2 Rationale of the Study

With the increasing intricacies in facade materials, aesthetic, performance, regulatory compliance requirements, specification and technology, the facade project management becomes thoughtful and complex. There are tasks to make sensible decisions by the proper parties at the right levels for the right selection of facades and its execution. Hence this research study will provide basic information's for further studies to identify the criteria effects the decisions in the selection of façades and to explore the feasibility of integrated decision making process in the project management of facades for the tall building of UAE.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this research study is as follows:

1. To explore the criteria effects the decisions in the selection of facades of Tall buildings Constructed in United Arab Emirates.

1.4 Review of Literature

Literature review helps to have a better understanding on facades particularly about facade project management related to tall buildings, recent research on selection of facades especially related to tall buildings, construction management concepts and initiatives, communication and knowledge management in construction and Integrated decision making Process and its feasibility. Authors, Helen Garmstonl, Wei Pan and Pieter de Wilde ^[2] of Plymouth University, Drake Circus, Plymouth, PL4 8AA, UK briefs in “Decision-making in facade selection for multi-storey buildings” that in current building practice, facade selection appears to be largely driven by cost considerations and building aesthetics. However, given the many demands on buildings, this approach can expose the real estate businesses and building inhabitants to risk. Authors did not attempt to explain the types of facades and its performance requirement rather talks about the share of curtain wall in a building cost wise and the need of sustainable designs and the ingredients of design are briefed. Tall buildings are required to comply certain legal drivers, such as building code of practice, as per industry standard or as per local authority manual.

It is also noteworthy to high light that the limited and insufficient literature in the field motivated Council on Tall buildings and Urban Habitat (CTBUH) to publish a “Road Map on the Future needs of Tall Buildings” with the editors Philip Old Field, Dario Trabuccu and Antony Wood. William Baker the trustee of CTBUH encouraged all in his speech on September 2013 that there is a need for research in all aspects of tall buildings. Unfortunately, in the area of façade industry there is strangely little recognized research.

1.5 Research Gap

Research gap” is defined as an area of research that is significantly immature and/or is suffering from a significant lack of available information and knowledge in the field. **William Baker, Skidmore, Owings & Merrill said**, “Each discipline involved in tall buildings is continually evolving its ‘science,’ but also has immediate problems to solve on current projects. One cannot wait to build until we know all there is to know. Conversely, just because we are currently creating buildings, we cannot forget that we must broaden our knowledge and extend the science of tall buildings.”

1.6 Research Methods

Data collection methods may be divided into the primary data collection and the secondary data collection. The secondary data is the form of data sets that have been previously

collected. Regarding building statistics secondary data Published by the Council on Tall Buildings and Urban Habitat (CTBUH) has been used. Cluster analysis has been followed for the identification of tall buildings in UAE and primary data has been collected through site survey regarding the type of facades employed for the buildings. A survey has been conducted among 200 façade industry professionals as follows.

FIG 1.1 NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS - 200

Source : Questionnaire Survey

1.7 Facades of Super Tall buildings in UAE

Building envelope remains one of the most important exterior elements in tall building and for the building functionality. Aluminum and Glazed metal curtain wall / cladding covers over 90 percent of the external envelope of the building facades of super tall buildings of UAE. Usually curtain wall or metal cladding consist of a rectangular mullion of vertical or horizontal transom framing with infill panels of glass or some other lightweight aluminum composite panel. Majority of the mega tall buildings fall into this category. Questionnaire survey has been conducted among 200 professionals selected from façade industry to understand “Façades of tall building has any Specific requirements compared to the facades of Low Rise building”. 187 professionals out 200 agreed that tall building facades has specific performance requirements and the criteria which influence in the selection of façades are, façade system performance, aesthetical factor, Delivery Time factor and price factor.

FIG 1.2 - Tall Building Facades has Specific Performance Requirements.

Source: Questionnaire survey

1.8 Criteria Effects the Decisions in the Selection of Facades

The criteria which influence in the selection of façades are, façade system performance, Aesthetical factor, Delivery Time factor and price factor.

FIG 1.3

FAÇADE AESTHETIC FACTOR

Aesthetic Factor is the design intent of the building as designed by the architect and engineered by the engineer, accepted by the client and approved by the local authority. This includes the geometrical shape of the building, related materials and its finish, architectural special elements and features etc. Generally aesthetic factor influence the Architects in the selection of facades decision making. Aesthetic factor is the uniqueness and identification of the building for its shape, appearance and to make it as iconic land mark building.

COST FACTOR

Price factor is the initial approved budget for the facade which includes all direct and indirect cost for design, engineering, procurement which includes shipping, taxes and insurance, fabrication, logistics, installation, testing, project management. Price factor also includes the direct and indirect maintenance cost during operation of the building. Price factor is an important factor which influence in the decisions especially for awarding the contract and procurement.

Fig 1.4

TIME FACTOR

Time factor is mainly related to the project delivery time. Time required to deliver the project on a particular date and time required to deliver a material on a specific time period. Contractual and procurement decisions are influenced by this factor. If the delivery period is long, alternative options will be chosen to deliver the project on time to avoid penalties and other liquidated damages. Hence time factor also influence the decision of selecting the facades or its related material.

PERFORMANCE FACTOR

Performance factor is the requirement of the façade to function as a wall. There are basic performance requirements, mandatory performance requirements and Optional performance requirements. Performance requirements are generally identified as follows:-

Fig 1.5

The Basic performance requirement are unavoidable to function as a wall. Failure of these performance will be the failure of façade. Structural Integrity is the resistance to the natural forces like wind load, Seismic load, gravity load etc. Façade should resist such imposed load as per the requirements of the specification of the project. Normally these requirements will be specified by the façade specialist consultant referring international standards of façade industry. Performance failure will lead to collapse of façade. Weather tightness is the requirement of resistance against water penetration and air infiltration. Failure of these performance requirements will affect the comfort of residents, destruction of carpets and furniture and increased cost for air conditioning. Movement requirements of facades are the provision to accommodate the building movement to wind, seismic etc and movement within the components due to thermal expansion.

Fig 1.6

The Mandatory performance requirements are requirements of the Municipality or local authority, civil defense, green building regulatory authority etc. Normally these requirements will be specified by the local authority for compliance. Failure in performance of such requirement will be sometimes consider as violation of law.

Fig 1.7

The Optional performance requirements are depends on nature and function of the building and its category type like hospital, hotel etc. Normally these requirements will be specified by the façade specialist consultant referring international standards of façade industry and local authority requirements. Failure in performance of such requirement will affect the comfort of the occupants.

Fig 1.8

1.9 Façade Selection Decision Making

Project management is the process and activity of scheduling, organizing, inspiring, and controlling the resource, time and task. The primary task of project management is to achieve all of the project goals and objectives while honoring the defined constraints. Normally the

primary constraints are scope, time, budget, quality and safety. It is important to know that in the project management of facades who takes the final decision in the selection of facades and approval of material related to facades and its performance requirement. The following is the result of survey questionnaire circulated among 200 professional respondents.

FIG 1.9 – Who Takes Final Decision

Source: Questionnaire survey

The decision making process in the project management of facades are mainly guided by its performance requirements, cost, time and aesthetics. Poor decisions in the project management can potentially expose developers, clients and occupiers of the Tall buildings to risks such as failure of the facade system, uncomfortable living due to poor performance and increased operational costs. With the increasing complexities in facade materials, aesthetic and performance and regulatory compliance requirements, specification and technology, the facade project management of tall buildings becomes deep and complex. There are challenges to make informed decisions by the appropriate parties at the right levels for the right selection of facades and its execution.

1.10 Conclusion

This study provided a clear understanding about the criteria effects the decision in the selection of façades of Super Tall buildings in UAE. The main finding gained through this

study is that Aesthetic factor, Cost factor, Time factor and Performance factor are the criteria which influence the decision making for selection of façades of Super Tall buildings. This information can be used for further study on project management of the façades of Tall buildings in UAE.

1.11 Recommendation for future Works

According to the results, many efforts need to be made in future work, including the following:-

- To Explore governing Criteria in the selection Facades for Tall Buildings
- Investigate the need and feasibility for integrated decision making process in the selection of Facades.

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